

TIME VARIATION OF THE COLOUR IN MIXTURES OF FERRIC CHLORIDE AND AMMONIUM THIOCYANATE

BY B. P. GYANI AND MISS RANI MISRA

Changes in the colour of mixtures of ferric chloride and ammonium thiocyanate with time have been investigated directly with the help of a Spekker absorptiometer. At least a part of the colour is temperature-reversible. A spontaneous reduction of ferric to ferrous ions is observed which is not affected by light. Addition of acids intensifies the colour at first, which is followed by a decay, affording somewhat similar absorption-time graphs as solutions which have been subjected to heating. The colour is of course intensified by increasing the ammonium thiocyanate concentration, and the initial rate of decay tends to slow down. There is an abrupt change in the slope of the absorption-time graph and the colour eventually tends to become stable at large concentrations of the thiocyanate. The complex nature of the changes is stressed and it is shown that none of the existing views concerning the nature of the colour or changes in it is adequate to explain all the observations.

A good deal of work appears in the literature concerning the red substance formed by the reaction between ferric and thiocyanate ions. Krüss and Moraht (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2054, 2061) considered it to be $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_2 \cdot 9\text{KCNS}$, the fading due to dilution being ascribed to dissociation of the double salt. Tarugi (*Gazzetta*, 1904, 34, 326) gave it the formula $\text{FeH}(\text{CNOS})_2$. Stoke and Cain (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 412) considered it to be the simple salt $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_3$, the fading being due to the reduction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_3$ to $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_2$. On the other hand, Bongiovanni (*Gazzetta*, 1907, 37, 472) ascribed it to hydrolysis, $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_3 \rightarrow \text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$. Philip and Bramley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 795) appear to be the only workers who followed the changes in mixtures of ferric chloride and ammonium thiocyanate over long periods. They established that some reduction took place on storage and that light did not affect the reaction even after four weeks' exposure.

Schlessinger and van Valkenburg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1212) prepared solid $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_3$ which furnished the same absorption spectrum in water, benzene and ether, being dimeric in the last two, and concluded that the red ion was $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_6^{3-}$. Bent and French (*ibid.*, 1941, 63, 568) used a spectrophotometer to test the equation

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{CNS}^-]}{[\text{Fe}_m(\text{CNS})_n]} = K$$

and found that if $m=1$, then $n=1$, leading to the formula $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_2^{2+}$ for the red ions.

Ricca and Farone (*Gazzetta*, 1946, 76, 78) studied the mixture conductometrically. They considered that depending upon concentration of ammonium thiocyanate, the mixture contained varying proportions of $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_3$, $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_2^+$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_6^{3-}$. Frank and Oswalt used a Coleman spectrophotometer. Some more papers have been reviewed in a recent work of Jatkar and Mattoo (*this Journal*, 1954, 31, 299). These authors have come to the conclusion that depending upon conditions, charged and uncharged complexes of the type $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_n$ may exist where n may have values from 1 to 6. We have used a Spekker absorptiometer on which colour changes may be followed directly and almost instantaneously, to re-investigate the problem.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

A stock solution of approximately 0.125 *M* ammonium thiocyanate (I) was prepared. A stock solution of ferric chloride containing 52.3 g. of the salt per litre (which was about ten years old) was used. It is important to specify the age of the solution since we have previously found that the hydrolysis of diluted ferric chloride solutions depends upon the age of the stock solution (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 499). This stock solution was diluted 100 times immediately before use (II). Since experiments with soda-glass bottles gave rise to erratic results (perhaps due to leaching of alkali) the mixtures were stored either in Jena glass bottles or in ordinary reagent bottles, coated inside with paraffin wax. One centimetre cells were used and the instrument was set to water = 1.000 with Ilford Spectrum Filter No. 602 (blue) unless specified otherwise.

Effect of Heating.—In one experiment equal volumes of (I) and (II) were mixed and enough water added to obtain an immediate Spekker reading of 0.140, i. e. an absorption of 0.860. The mixture was then divided into two portions. One was followed at room temperature on the Spekker (curve A, Fig. 1). The other was heated to boiling and followed similarly (curve B). Fig. 1 shows the plot of absorption against time in minutes. While the cold solution tends to decrease in absorption, the reverse is true of the boiled solution. Similar results were obtained in other experiments in which the proportion of water was decreased. The period taken by the two graphs to approach each other increased as the mixture became more concentrated.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

To investigate this matter further, 40 c.c. of (I) and (II) each and 120 c.c. of water were mixed. The mixture was divided into three portions. These were heated in water-baths rapidly to 50° , 70° and 90° respectively. The heating was stopped as soon as these solutions had attained the specified temperatures. The graphs of absorption against time are shown in Fig. 2. As the temperature is increased the absorption decreases. During the first two hours after heating, the absorption shows a slight increase in each case. Thereafter for the next two hours it is practically constant which is followed by a slow decrease of colour until a more or less steady small absorption is reached, which appears to be nearly constant for all the three curves though they started with quite different intensities of absorption. The view that the fading of colour on storage is produced by hydrolysis of the salt formed at first to ferric hydroxide, or the reduction of ferric ions to ferrous ions, fails to explain the existence of the initial increase.

Effects of Acids and KCl.—In the experiments described below, another stock solution of ferric chloride was used. It contained 46.34 g. of FeCl_3 per litre and was a year old. It was diluted 100 times prior to use as before (III). A mixture of 40 c.c. of (I) and (III) each and 120 c.c. of water was taken (initial absorption 0.951) and followed on the Spekker. Curve A, Fig. 3 shows the plot of absorption against time. When the mixture had attained an absorption of 0.558 (dotted horizontal line), 50 c.c. of the mixture was withdrawn and one drop of 2N-HCl added. The resulting graph B shows the subsequent changes counting from the moment of addition of the acid. The red colour showed an instantaneous partial recovery, but then declined, though at a smaller rate.

FIG. 4

FIG. 3

A few more quantitative experiments were also carried out. A mixture of 20 c.c. of (I) and (III) each and 110 c.c. of water was prepared (initial absorption 0.470) and divided into three portions. To the first was added 1 c.c. of $N/1$ -HCl (A), to the second 0.5 c.c. (B), and to the third 0.1 c.c. (C). The changes in these mixtures are shown by the corresponding graphs (Fig. 4). There is again observed a rise immediately after addition of the acid. The red colour remains steady for a day if enough acid is present (mixture $N/100$ or above) but an immediate decay may follow if the concentration is less.

The effect on the depth of colour by adding increasing quantities of HCl to a mixture of 5 c.c. of (I) and (III) each and 40 c.c. of water (initial absorption 0.180) has also been studied. At the end of the experiment 1.5 c.c. of $N/1$ -HCl had been added in the case of the upper graph and 15 c.c. of $N/10$ -HCl in the case of the lower graph (Fig. 5) so that weight of dry HCl added along any vertical line in the diagram was always the same. At the end the total volume was 51.5 c.c. in the first case and 65 c.c. in the second. The absorptions in the latter were therefore corrected for dilution, e.g., the actual absorption (0.580) corresponding to volume = 65 c.c. was multiplied by $65/50$ to obtain the absorption if the volume had remained 50 c.c. Other absorptions were similarly corrected. These corrected values appear in Fig. 5. We note that a maximum absorption is attained in each case which is not increased further after the mixture is a little over $N/50$ in respect of HCl (about 1.2 c.c. N -HCl added). If the absorption were determined solely by the weight of dry HCl added, the two graphs should have coincided.

FIG. 5

The addition of HCl in the above two experiments was completed within an hour. In another experiment, in which the addition of HCl was stopped after adding 10 c.c. of the acid and again resumed after two hours, the absorption rose. The concluding portion of the curve was then located higher than the first. This anomaly is easily understood with reference to Fig. 3 or Fig. 4, which show that there is an intensification of colour with the increase in time after addition of the acid. As expected, the colour is found to depend on the manner of adding the acid and also its strength. It is of significance, however, that nitric acid brings about a larger deepening of colour than the corresponding concentrations of HCl, but the final effect is the same. KCl is not indifferent and produces a distinct lowering in the intensity of the colour.

In another series of experiments we prepared a series of mixtures of the compositions, noted below :

A	=	5 c.c. of III	+	5 c.c. of 5% NH ₄ CNS	+	65 c.c. of water,	mixture = 0.042 N-NH ₄ CNS
B	=	"	"	"	+	60	" " = 0.085 "
C	=	"	"	"	+	55	" " = 0.127 "
D	=	"	"	"	+	50	" " = 0.170 "
E	=	"	"	"	+	45	" " = 0.212 "

To 50 c.c. of each solution 1 c.c. of N-HCl was added. Changes in these mixtures were then followed on the Spekker. Changes in the remaining 20-25 c.c. portions (blanks) were also followed. The results appear in Fig. 6 (blanks) and Fig. 7 (with HCl). It is interesting to note that in the absence of HCl a large concentration of ammonium thiocyanate not only develops a deeper red initially but may also check the decay of colour better. An upper limit to the initial intensity of the colour appears to have been reached at 20 c.c. of 5% NH₄CNS (*i.e.*, about 0.17N-NH₄CNS in the mixture). Considering the lower flat portion of the curve E, it seems that a possibility exists that if concentration of ammonium thiocyanate is increased further a stable red colour may be obtained. This expectation is completely belied by the curve F (5 c.c. of III + 70 c.c. of 5% NH₄CNS). Curves for mixtures saturated with NH₄CNS are also shown.

Fig. 7 shows that the presence of HCl completely alters the nature of changes. The intensity of colour in any mixture rises very rapidly at first, a peak is reached in about 1 to 2 hours, followed by a slow decline. The peak is higher, the higher the concentration of ammonium thiocyanate and appears to converge again at a concentration of about 0.17 N thiocyanate. During the decline B, C and D again bunch together, but surprisingly enough, A shows the smallest decline and E, the largest.

As fading sets in, ferrous ions may be detected in any mixture whether acid is present or not. Addition of K₂Fe(CN)₆ produces a blue coloration or precipitate. The reduction appears to be larger when HCl is present. It appears that a large part of the decline in colour is due to reduction. For the same concentration of HCl in the mixture, the reduction appears to be larger, the larger the concentration of ammonium thiocyanate. A large concentration of ammonium thiocyanate therefore may produce

a large initial intensity of colour, but at the same time gives rise to a larger decline. It may thus be possible, to understand the courses of all the graphs in Fig. 7.

FIG. 6

FIG. 7

DISCUSSION

We have established the following experimental facts and any mechanism of production and stability of the red colour would have to account for them : (A) A general slow fading for all solutions irrespective of deepening by any factor; (B) fading of the red colour by temperature increase and slow recovery of the same at lower temperatures; (C) slow reduction to ferrous ions; (D) intensification of colour by acids, the efficiency being in the order $\text{HNO}_3 > \text{HCl}$.

It is evident that the existing theories are unable to cover all the present observations nor are our results sufficient to lead to some convincing conclusions. To fix our ideas it is perhaps helpful to write down a scheme for the changes observed such as follows.

The letters correspond to the observations noted above. Heating produces enhanced hydrolysis (action B) and depresses the colour. Addition of acid depresses

the hydrolysis in the first instance (action D) followed by the formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_2$, etc. and restoration of colour. It is not possible at this stage to say whether the observations under (A) and (C), viz., a general slow fading and reduction of ferric ions, are identical. Perhaps these actions may be irreversible. They lead to unknown products. As far as FeOH^{2+} is concerned, it appears that action (B), viz.

should take place immediately on addition of acid [as also the subsequent reaction leading to the formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_2$, etc.], but a portion of the action restoring colour is slow (there was always excess of ammonium thiocyanate in the mixture). The actual mechanism may therefore not be quite so simple. The stronger restoring effect of nitric acid may be due to the fact that it has no common ion with the reacting materials. These suggestions are naturally tentative and a more satisfactory explanation has to await further work which is in progress.

The authors thank Shri N. L. Vidyarthi for the loan of the $\hat{\text{S}}$ pekker and Dr. A. P. B. Sinha, now of the National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, for helpful discussions.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE,
PATNA 5.

Received December 9, 1953.